

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

RICHARDSON MODEL AS A MEANS FOR THE MILITARY EXPENDITURES POLICY ADJUSTMENT AND ITS ARMAMENTS CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract

Current paper is devoted to the study of the use of Richardson's model as a means for the adjustment of countries military expenditures policies acting in the region of their interests. As the model we are considering a system of differential equations and are defining a general solution.

Being interested in the study of the application for real world example a simulation Richardson model for five countries is given. Mutual threats between acting countries are considered. Farther, number of threats are defining and considering as constants, assessing outcomes of countries.

Keywords: Richadso model, military policy, adjustment, threat, ordinary differential equations.

1. Introduction

Richardson was the first who considered countries armaments model. The model he developed provided the analysis of countries armaments processes focused on wars and conflicts. The model is based on mathematical analysis of the insecurity of nations. Richardson's model considered in¹ is a system of differential equations. In current study we will define a model as a system of five differential equations presenting the change of the volume of the military expenses of one country depending from the volume of expenses of other countries.

We showed that proposed approach provides the possibility for the presentation, solving and analyzing model, where individual countries are cooperating and/or mutually infusing in one economic – political region of their interests. It's assumed that these countries are acting in a similar way of Richardson model: one of these countries follows the strategy aimed at depleting the military resources of another country, either acting independently or in the cooperation with other involved in the model country. Countries whose policy is aimed at obtaining a favorable position in the region for solving own goals, cooperating with the countries involved in the conflict, as well as with a group of other countries having their own economic – political interests in the region are also highlighted. It's assumed that countries have their own goals and strategies in relation to influence on each of the countries are considered. Thus, to value the impacts between countries we consider country's military expenses as the assessment of country's state as the outcome of the interaction between countries. Consequently, country's military spending has same meaning as in the Richardson model.

Thus, in current paper we will consider a system of five countries as follows:

- i) countries 1 and 2 are infusing each other;

ii) countries 3,4, and 5 are interacting separately or in cooperation with one of 1 2 country are infusing or providing a support.

2. Definitions and notations

We will follow the approach considered in² proposed an extension of Lotka-Volterra model and use it for the study of Richardson's model given as follows³

$$\frac{dp_i}{dt} = g_i p_i(t) + \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq 5, i \neq j} d_{i,j} p_j(t), \quad (1)$$

where i) $p_i(t)$ is the military expenses of i -th county, ii) $g_i p_i(t)$ represents either the growth or decreasing rate of the country, iii) $d_{i,j}$ is a constant representing the number of the threats of j -th county to i -th county, iv) we will assume that depending from the sign in front of the coefficient $d_{i,j}$ the rate $d_{i,j} p_j(t)$ could be positive or negative. Let us consider the system of ordinary differential equations as the example of (1) as follows:

$$\frac{dp_i}{dt} = g_i p_i(t) + \sum_{1 \leq i, j \leq 5, j \neq i} d_{i,j} p_j(t) \quad (2)$$

, where $i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$ Assume that $t \in [0, T]$, $p_k(0) = p_{k0}, k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$, where as we proposed $p_k(t)$ is military expenditures of k -th country, $k = 1, 2, \dots, 5$.

Mutual threats between countries In this section we'll present threats between countries. Mutual economic political interests of countries and the consequences of their armaments.

¹ Richardson, Lewis F (1960) Arms and Insecurity. Pittsburgh, PA: Boxwood

² A.Arakelyan, L.Makaryan Model of territorial conflict and international military cooperation, Journal of Yerevan University Economics, (3), 2021p.56-72

³ Schrod, Philip A (1981) Preserving Arms Distributions in a Multi-Polar World. Monograph Series in World Affairs, Graduate School of International Studies 18(4). Denver, CO: University of Denver Press.

All further references are given without changing the original.

I. Iran against Azerbaijan.

1.1. Russian political scientist and expert on the Middle East and Caucasus Stanislav Tarasov⁴ noted that Iran rejects Azerbaijan efforts to violate the boarder between Armenia and Azerbaijan and create the corridor connecting Azerbaijan with Nakhchivan. He mentioned that the topic "Zangezur corridor" introduced Azerbaijan according to the statement signed between Armenia, Azerbaijan and Russia on November 9, of 2020. As the statement presents the road should be under the control of the Russian federal Security Service. However, Azerbaijan's and Turkey's demands are to kick out Russia and take the road under their control. According to Tarasov, Pashinyan's goal is to normalize relations with Turkey whose president set up a condition for the creation of a corridor between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan. Due to political and economic conditions, Iran is not satisfied with the existing results concerning to the solution of the Karabakh problem and the creation of a corridor between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan. Iran set up the demand to be a participant of the processes related to negotiations. Currently the Statement has been signed by the presidents of Russia and Azerbaijan and the Prime Minister of Armenia on November 9, 2020. Turkey sought to take part in the process of signing this Statement but Putin rejected such participation. Historically Karabakh is zone of influence of Iran and therefore decisions regarding the creation of communications, the conclusion of a peace treaty between the Armenia and Azerbaijan, the determination of the status of Karabakh cannot be executed without the participation of Iran.

Therefore, Iran does not recognize the Statements of the three sides of Russia, Azerbaijan and Armenia without its participation and is even ready to send troops into the disputed region.

1.2. Iran armament politics

Iran Develops Its First Domestic Hypersonic Ballistic Missile by Nigar Bayramli⁵

Iran is currently under economic and political pressure from the United States, the European Union, Israel and Saudi Arabia, Turkey and Azerbaijan. In particular, the economic and political interests of Iran and these countries clash in relation to the South Caucasus. To resolve conflict situations and create conditions for fruitful participation in resolving conflict situations, Iran is facilitated by the development of the aerospace industry. Development of nuclear technology is explained by the creation of hypersonic missiles, which, unlike those currently available, can carry nuclear weapons along a complex trajectory at a speed of more than five times the speed of sound, making them difficult to intercept. Brigadier General Amir-Ali Hajizadeh, Head of the Aerospace Division of the Islamic

Revolutionary Guards Corps (IRGC), said: "This missile can hit the enemy's anti-missile systems and is a great leap forward in the development of missiles." Iran continues to cooperate with Russia in the field of satellite development, and in particular, in August, the Khayyam satellite, which was built and launched by Russia on behalf of Iran, went into orbit from the Russian-controlled Baikonur Cosmodrome in Kazakhstan. The Iranian space agency said the satellite would be used for agricultural and water resources planning, while the Russian embassy in Tehran said the spacecraft was designed for non-military purposes. Iran's satellite program and its nuclear activities have attracted the attention of the United States, other Western countries and in particular the neighboring countries of the South Caucasus, Turkey, Israel and Saudi Arabia. These stars fear that "long-range ballistic technology, which is used to put satellites into orbit, could also be used to launch nuclear warheads. Tehran has repeatedly denied having such intentions." Under the circumstances, these countries note the growing military threat from Iran. In particular, such a threat can be perceived by Azerbaijan and Turkey. Unlike these countries, Iran's success in the field of air technologies and its nuclear program can find significant support and understanding from Russia, which sees Iran as a reliable partner for resolving the conflict in the South Caucasus with the participation of Iran. 1.3. Iran Warns Against 'Border Changes' As Armenia, Azerbaijan Clash, Iran International Newsroom⁶

According to the cited statement, Iran warns against "changing borders" against the background of the clash between Armenia and Azerbaijan. The current situation was the result of a long-term conflict between neighbors Armenia and Azerbaijan. The economic and political interests of Iran justify its policy of unacceptability of changes in the existing borders between the two countries. Iran, according to the official government news website IRNA, said Tehran was "watching this issue closely" and offered help to resolve the differences. Iran said that "the escalation of years of hostilities between the countries of the South Caucasus has raised fears that in the post-Soviet world, in addition to Russia's invasion of Ukraine, a second full-fledged war may break out." In response to Azerbaijan's policy of launching a large-scale war, Iran warned that there should be "no military solution" for the region. The conflict must be resolved through diplomacy.

1.3. Iran plays its cards in the South Caucasus

As noted Yeghia Tashjian Tashjian's Take, Columns⁷ Iran plays its cards in the South Caucasus.

At the beginning of 2022, Iran's foreign policy changed. This was prompted by Russia's awareness of the importance of the North-South trade route. This led to the fact that Iran changed its relations with Azerbaijan, and also increased interaction with Armenia. Given the growing role of Iran in the region, Baku has reduced

⁴Tarasov: Iran may not recognize peace treaty between Yerevan and Baku and send troops (news.am) <https://news.am/eng/news/724783.html>

⁵ <https://caspiannews.com/news-detail/iran-develops-its-first-domestic-hypersonic-ballistic-missile-2022-11-10-56/>

⁶ <https://www.iranintl.com/en/202209137964>

⁷ <https://armenianweekly.com/2022/05/25/iran-plays-its-cards-in-the-south-caucasus/>

political pressure on Yerevan. Iran's activity in protecting its geopolitical interests would be based on determining the role of Armenia and Azerbaijan in resolving Iran's regional trade and economic interests. Iran is currently distinguished as a country that has the potential in the field of conducting diplomatic negotiations aimed at creating conditions for the development of the South Caucasus region in conditions of peace that meets the interests of the countries of the region. Relations with the countries of the region and countries with economic and political interests have shown that the ways proposed by Iran to resolve the conflict can satisfy the requirements of the countries of the region and at the same time meet the interests of Iran itself. Detente of relations with Azerbaijan

On March 11, 2022, Azerbaijan and Iran signed an agreement on the creation of new railways, roads and energy supply lines connecting the southern territories of Karabakh/Artsakh seized by Azerbaijan with the exclave of Nakhichevan. Dogowu proposes the creation of a new highway, 55 kilometers long, starting at Zankelan. The agreement involves the creation of two railway bridges and a road bridge across the border river Araks. As a result of this highway will pass through northern Iran and provide a connection to the Nakhichevan village of Ordubad.

"The Iranian political scientist Vali Kaleji in his article "Construction of roads and railways between Zangilan and Nakhchivan: views from Baku and Tehran" emphasizes that this project is of geo-economic importance for Azerbaijan and Iran."

The articles of the agreement on the creation of communication routes passing through the territories of Iran and Azerbaijan provide an opportunity to strengthen Azerbaijan in terms of communication with the regions of Azerbaijan and, very importantly, connect Azerbaijan with Nakhchivan. The most important feature of the agreement proposed by Iran is also that "the 55-kilometer highway through Iran will become an alternative to the Zangezur Corridor," which Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev insisted on after the tripartite statement of November 9, 2020. With the help of Iran, this alternative route will take some pressure off Armenia's shoulders, as Baku threatened to gain a corridor through the strategic Syunik region in southern Armenia and cut Armenia's border with Iran." At the same time, Azerbaijan will establish a connection with Nakhichevan through Iran, which in the future will provide additional Iranian levers of influence on Azerbaijan. We also note that the fake Zangezur corridor is a plan developed and discussed in the think tanks of NATO, Turkey and the Zionist regime. Obviously, it is directed against the political and economic interests of Iran, Russia, China and India. Consequently, Iran, Russia, China and India, having military and economic potential, "are able to prevent geopolitical changes on the southern borders of Armenia in order to implement the fake Zangezur corridor in accordance with the UN Charter, which prohibits any change in international

borders." Iran, proceeding primarily from its geopolitical interests, managed to attract Armenia and Azerbaijan to mutually beneficial cooperation. At the same time, Iran's interaction with the countries of the region, taking into account the interests of Russia, China and India, made it possible to reduce the risk of a conflict situation developing and exclude the possibility of a large-scale war on the territories of Armenia and Azerbaijan. "Iran's interaction with Azerbaijan on the alternative 'corridor' removed the military and political pressure on Armenia in connection with the Azerbaijani threat over Syunik, but at the same time left Armenia isolated for some time from regional communication and trade projects." 1.5. Iran will not tolerate any border changes in region, army chief says⁸

Major General Mohammad Bagheri, Chief of Staff of the Iranian Armed Forces, said that Iran would not tolerate any changes in borders in the region. Mohammad Bagheri called on Armenia and Azerbaijan to solve their problems through dialogue.

"As we have repeatedly stated, we will not tolerate changes in the borders of the countries of the region," Bagheri said. "We advise Azerbaijan and Armenia to solve their problems through dialogue." Despite this, Azerbaijani forces launched a massive offensive against Armenia just after midnight on September 13, inflicting artillery and drone strikes on Armenian military positions and civilian settlements. Thanks to Russian promptings late on the evening of September 14, hostilities ceased at 20:00 local time. In turn, the Secretary of the Security Council of Armenia, Armen Grigoryan, shortly after midnight announced that Yerevan and Baku had agreed on a ceasefire mediated by the international community.

1.4. Iran's protests against Azerbaijan's propaganda campaign against Iran

The Iranian Foreign Ministry summoned the ambassador of the Republic of Azerbaijan to Tehran to lodge a protest over the propaganda campaign waged by the country's officials and media against Iran expressed regret over the situation and promised to immediately convey Iran's protest to the authorities in Baku. 1.7. Iran, Russia Start Joint Naval Drill in Indian Ocean⁹

Iran, Russia Start of Joint Naval Drill in Indian Ocean showed significance of the bilateral relations between Kremlin and Teheran. The importance of cooperation between Moscow and Tehran showed additional threat directed to Ankara and Baku setting and continuing aggressive regional political economic behavior against Tehran and Yerevan. In addition Russia maintained the South Caucasus as a region of sphere of influence. "The purposes of this drill are to enhance security of international maritime trade, confront maritime piracy and terrorism, and exchange information." Thus, Russia and Iran became countries which participation in the construction of future political economic policy of South Caucasus. It should be noted that the Iranian army exercised also "expansion of bilateral re-

⁸ <https://www.panorama.am/ru/news/2022/09/22/Iranian-army-chief/2733590>

⁹ <https://www.themoscowtimes.com/2021/02/16/iran-russia-start-joint-naval-drill-in-indian-ocean-a72979>

lations" with Russia. Iran, China and Russia held a similar drill in the area in 2019, and the Islamic republic participated in "Caucas 2020" drills held in Russia last September. 1.8. Iran Calls Close Relations with Russia "Decisive Response" to US Sanctions¹⁰

Iranian President Ebrahim Raisi has described close cooperation with Russia as the most "decisive response" to US sanctions, amid mounting evidence of Russia's use of Iranian drones in its war against Ukraine.

IRAN --The head of Iran's Revolutionary Guard Corps Hossein Salami (R) watches a launch of missiles during a military drill in an unknown location in central Iran, January 15, 2021

Iran's Revolutionary Guards began on Monday major military exercises along the country's borders with Armenia and Azerbaijan amid lingering fears of renewed fighting between the two South Caucasus states.

The war games, described by Iranian news agencies as "massive," are taking place near a stretch of the Arax river that separates northwestern Iran from Armenia's Syunik province as well as Azerbaijan's Nakhichevan exclave and districts south of Nagorno-Karabakh recaptured by the Azerbaijani army during the 2020 war. New reports showed available threats against Azerbaijan from Iran proposing more practical and mutually beneficial resolution of the construction of communications means between South Caucasus countries. The Iran's military economic power should be the mean providing acceptance by Azerbaijan and Turkey the proposal of Iranian political and economic regional policy. 1.9. Iran's military starts "massive" drills on Azerbaijani border¹¹

Tehran appears alarmed both by Azerbaijan's saber-rattling against Armenia and by a new EU monitoring mission to Armenia's border with Iran. Screenshot of Iranian media footage of its armed forces crossing the Aras River on a pontoon bridge. Iran's military is conducting large-scale military drills on its border with Azerbaijan, including practicing crossings of the Aras River, which defines a large part of the border between the two states. Drills should be a mean showing the threat to Azerbaijan and Turkey against their aggressive policy against Armenia to change Armenian borders as well to build new transport link connecting Azerbaijan's exclave of Nakhchivan with the Azerbaijani mainland, a route that Baku calls the "Zangezur corridor." The route would pass along Armenia's border with Iran, with uncertain consequences for Armenia-Iran commerce.

1.5. In recent days, Iran has threatened to destroy Azerbaijan alongside Israel in a video clip: "Israel don't stray too far from your path"¹²

1.6. As reported earlier today, a large Iranian spy network has been exposed in Azerbaijan: such a state-

ment from the State Security Service is an a priori number one news story.¹³ Here we have the complete set of less than gentlemanly methods employed by the Iranian secret services: recruitment of Azerbaijani citizens who go to Iran for education or even medical treatment, attempts to use them to organize religious and political uprisings in Azerbaijan (we saw real examples in Nardaran and Ganja), and so on. This time the Iranian agents were engaged in actual military espionage. Their handlers from Tehran and Qom were interested in the dates of military exercises in the Caspian Sea, the specifications of the Israeli and Turkish UAVs used by Azerbaijani border guards, and the coordinates of the military bases in Salyan, Lankaran and Fizuli... There is a reason why the criminal case was initiated on charges of national treason.

1.9. Iranian flag flies in front of the UN office building in Vienna (photo credit: REUTERS/LISI NIESNER/FILE PHOTO)¹⁴

Iranian agents are scouring the world for dissidents and spying on countries from Azerbaijan to the US. The reports this week show an increasingly dangerous web of Iranian plots all around the world, from the Caucasus to the US and UK.

This is important because the reports sometimes make it appear that one country or another has suddenly found an Iranian regime plot, when in fact the systematic Iranian threat is much larger and more robust than just one network of spies and agents in one place and another network somewhere else.

Iran's global threats are not new phenomena, Iran has often carried out plots all over the world, targeting dissidents, targeting Israel, or other missions. However, as Iran is increasingly in the spotlight for its crackdown on protesters there is more alarm in the West and at international organizations such as the UN regarding Iran's activities.

1.7. Treaty of Gulistan

The **Treaty of Gulistan** (Russian: Гюлистанский договор; Persian: عهدنامه گلستان) was a peace treaty concluded between the Russian Empire and Iran on 24 October 1813 in the village of Gulistan (now in the Goranboy District of Azerbaijan) as a result of the first full-scale Russo-Persian War (1804 to 1813). The peace negotiations were precipitated by the successful storming of Lankaran by General Pyotr Kotlyarevsky on 1 January 1813. It was the first of the series of treaties (the last being the Akhal Treaty) signed between Qajar Iran and Imperial Russia that forced Persia to cede or recognize Russian influence over the territories that formerly were part of Iran.^{[1][2]}

The treaty confirmed the ceding and inclusion of what is now Dagestan, eastern Georgia, most of the Republic of Azerbaijan and parts of northern Armenia from Iran into the Russian Empire.

¹⁰ <https://www.azatutyun.am/a/32088258.html>

¹¹ <https://eurasianet.org/irans-military-starts-massive-drills-on-azerbaijani-border>

¹² <https://aze.media/why-iran-threatens-azerbaijan-together-with-israel/>

¹³ <https://aze.media/iran-sows-the-wind-and-crosses-red-lines/>

¹⁴ <https://aze.media/increase-in-iranian-global-threats-spear-headed-by-the-irgc/>

II. Russian threats against Azerbaijan

2.1. Russian Defense Ministry confirms¹⁵ violation of ceasefire in Artsakh by Azerbaijani Armed Forces and puts forward a demand to Azerbaijan to stop the violation of ceasefire regime. On November 14, 2022 The Russian Ministry of Defense confirmed that the ceasefire regime in Artsakh was violated by the Armed Forces of Azerbaijan. From the Azerbaijani post on November 12, the Azerbaijani side opened fire from small arms on a local resident who was carrying out agricultural work. As a result a resident was injured and agricultural machinery was damaged. In response to this incident, the Russian peacekeeping forces, with the participation of the Azerbaijani side, are conducting investigations at the request of the Russian side. Russia put forward a demand in relation to Azerbaijan to comply with the conditions of the ceasefire regime. 2.2. Russia deploys troops to Nagorno-Karabakh after ceasefire deal signed

Russian peacekeeping troops deployed to the war-ravaged enclave of Nagorno-Karabakh in the early hours of Tuesday (10 November) as part of a Russia-brokered ceasefire deal. Reactions in Yerevan suggest that the deal seals a defeat for Armenia and territorial gains ...

Russia is an ally of Armenia, an impoverished former Soviet republic of less than 3 million people. Moscow already has a military base in the northwest of Armenia, and sent 2,000 troops as peacekeepers to Nagorno-Karabakh, an enclave of Azerbaijan populated by ethnic Armenians, under the accord that ended last year's fighting in the area.

"Two strongholds of the 102nd Russian military base were established in the Syunik region," the Interfax news agency cited Pashinyan as saying in an address to the Armenian parliament, referring to Russia's existing base in Armenia.

"This is an additional security guarantee not only for the Syunik region but for Armenia," Pashinyan was quoted as saying.

Syunik is a strategic strip of Armenia located between Azerbaijan, the Azeri exclave of Nakhchivan, and Iran. The Armenian defence minister said in February that Yerevan wanted Russia to expand its presence and deploy troops closer to Azerbaijan. read more

Pashinyan has remained in office in an acting capacity after resigning as prime minister last month in a dispute with the army over blame for the outcome of last year's war, seen as a humiliating defeat. A new election is set for 20 June. He announced his resignation a day after US President Joe Biden declared Armenians the victims of genocide by Turkey in World War One, recognition Armenians had sought for decades.

2.3. New Russian Naval Doctrine Assigns Expanded Role to Caspian Flotilla¹⁶

The Russian Navy corvette *Veliky Ustyug*, a small missile ship in the Caspian Flotilla, takes part in a military parade on the Neva River on Russian Navy Day in 2021 (Source: Peter Kovalev/TASS). One aspect of the new doctrine, however—its elevation of the Russian naval presence in the Caspian—has received far less attention; but it may ultimately be more important. That conclusion reflects the additional threat to contain the aggressive policy directed against the countries of the South Caucasus and in particular Armenia and Iran. Ultimately, the doctrine contributes to the involvement of India and China in the economic and political development of the conflict region in peace. 2.4. Russian Navy Launches Caspian Sea Drills¹⁷ Currently, 1 February 2022 Russia's Navy has launched drills involving 20 warships in the Caspian Sea. The Video published by the Defense Ministry shows the ships from the Caspian Fleet departing from their base in Makhachkala in the republic of Dagestan. The video Drills showed the power of Russian Caspian Fleet forces. "Artillery boat and minesweeper crews will carry out mining support tasks for the deployment of Caspian Fleet forces and defense against anti-submarine and sabotage [attacks] ... The Caspian Fleet sailors will search for mines using trawls and practice destroying them with live-firing from service weapons," the statement said. Russian Navy Launched Caspian Sea Drills called to Turkey and Azerbaijan to be careful an don't initiate new aggressive steps against countries of the conflicting region including Armenia and Iran. Actually, drills were in the context of political economic policy of China and India.

2.5. Iran, Russia Start Joint Naval Drill in Indian Ocean¹⁸

Iran, Russia Start of Joint Naval Drill in Indian Ocean showed significance of the bilateral relations between Kremlin and Teheran. The importance of cooperation between Moscow and Tehran showed additional threat directed to Ankara and Baku setting and continuing aggressive regional political economic behavior against Tehran and Yerevan. In addition Russia maintained the South Caucasus as a region of sphere of influence. "The purposes of this drill are to enhance security of international maritime trade, confront maritime piracy and terrorism, and exchange information." Thus, Russia and Iran became countries which participation in the construction of future political economic policy of South Caucasus. It should be noted that the Iranian army exercised also "expansion of bilateral relations" with Russia. Iran, China and Russia held a similar drill in the area in 2019, and the Islamic republic participated in "Caucus 2020" drills held in Russia last September.

2.6. Russian, Iranian presidents discuss current issues on bilateral agenda¹⁹

¹⁵ <https://news.am/eng/news/730119.html>

¹⁶ Paul Goble, Eurasia Daily Monitor Volume: 19 Issue: 125 <https://jamestown.org/program/new-russian-naval-doctrine-assigns-expanded-role-to-caspian-flotilla/>

¹⁷ <https://www.themoscowtimes.com/2022/02/17/russian-navy-launches-caspian-sea-drills-a76426>

¹⁸ <https://www.themoscowtimes.com/2021/02/16/iran-russia-start-joint-naval-drill-in-indian-ocean-a72979>

¹⁹ <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/middle-east/russian-iranian-presidents-discuss-current-issues-on-bilateral-agenda-/2736477>

On 12.11.2022 Russian, Iranian presidents discuss current issues on bilateral agenda. The meeting held in Busra Nur Cakmak.

Russian President Vladimir Putin and his Iranian counterpart Ebrahim Raisi discussed "current issues on bilateral agenda" over phone, a Kremlin statement said Saturday. "The leaders discussed a number of current issues on the bilateral agenda with an emphasis on the continued building up of interaction in politics, trade and the economy, including transport and logistics," said the statement. They agreed that the contacts between Russian and Iranian institutions will be increased, it added. As a result the threat against Turkey and Azerbaijan appeared.

2.7. Russian MP threatened Azerbaijan with a nuclear strike, the Kremlin had to intervene²⁰

Deputy of the Russian State Duma Mikhail Delyagin, speaking at the state television of the Russian Federation, called for the "punishment" of Azerbaijan for "aggressive actions" in Karabakh. He also conducted a survey on the topic of whether "is it worth it to hit the oil industry of Azerbaijan with nuclear weapons". The Kremlin press secretary Dmitry Peskov and the official representative of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Maria Zakharova, had to intervene in this matter. Only after that Delyagin apologized to the Azerbaijanis. **III. Turkish politics in South Caucasus.**

3.1. Erdogan²¹ notes that the situation in the South Caucasus remains unstable. He confirms that Azerbaijan is striving to normalize the situation in the South Caucasus. He stated this at the Summit of the Organization of Turkic States in Samarkand in Uzbekistan. In response to Azerbaijan's victory in the 44-day war with Armenia, he congratulated Azerbaijan and noted Azerbaijan's desire for the establishment of the peace, as well as its just struggle to establish territorial integrity and fulfill the conditions of the November 9, 2020 Statement. 3.2. A key point for Turkey: the deal calls for the opening of a transport corridor between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan²². According to the statement given by P. Zalewski the key point for Turkey is the deal calls for the opening of a transport corridor between Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan, its western exclave. This means a connection between Baku and Nakhchivan, its western exclave. This means a connection between Baku and Turkey. 3.3. Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey start joint military exercises²³.

"Caucasian Eagle-2022" are joint military exercises being carried out by Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey. According to the information of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia, the opening ceremony of "Caucasian Eagle-2022" was held on October 11 in the village of Mukhrovani, at the military base of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia. The goal of the exercises is to

achieve better synchronization in the actions of the special operations forces of the three countries, and to improve the effectiveness of command and control in a multinational environment. The units participating in the exercises will share their experience in conducting fire and medical training, combat operations in populated areas and special operations. As a result joint military exercises are threat against Russia, Iran and Armenia 3.4. Armenia facing both external and internal challenges. Expert on Turkey Ruben Melkonyan concluded that Armenia has found itself in a difficult situation, facing both external and internal challenges²⁴. He criticized in his book Ideological Constitution of the "Era of Peace" (a review of Jirair Libaridian's book "Armenia-Turkey: Statehood, History, Politics") in Yerevan on Saturday, through pointing to the "fake news campaign" among Armenian society concerning peace with Turkey and Azerbaijan. Currently no prerequisites are in place to achieve it," the expert claimed. Among Armenian authorities suggesting the possibility of peace relations between Armenian-Turkish and Armenian-Azerbaijani and did not take into account the aggressive nature of Azerbaijan and Turkey, he highlighted the "studies of the former chief advisor to first Armenian President Levon Ter-Petrosyan, former Ambassador-at-Large and Deputy Foreign Minister Gerard Jirair Libaridian, summarized in his book Armenia-Turkey: Statehood, History, Politics."

IV. Azerbaijan's threats against Armenia

4.1. Azerbaijan's troops enter first district handed over by Armenia²⁵

The troops of Azerbaijan entered the region bordering on Nagorno-Karabakh. The Armenian armed forces left the area, but nevertheless the Azerbaijani armed forces entered the Aghdam region, one of the three to be ceded, the Azerbaijani Defense Ministry said. Armenia handed over the Kelbajar region, sandwiched between Nagorno-Karabakh and Armenia on November 25, and the Lachin region - by December 1. The changes that took place in Nagorno-Karabakh took place at the end of September 2020 as a result of a large-scale brutal war declared by Azerbaijan to Armenia and lasting for six. Hostilities were stopped on November 9, 2020 as part of the peace agreement concluded between Armenia and Azerbaijan with the participation of Russia. About 2,000 Russian peacekeeping forces have been deployed to the region's capital, Stepanakert, and have set up checkpoints and observation posts along the strategic Lachin corridor linking Nagorno-Karabakh to Armenia. 4.2. Pashinyan slams Azeri shooting at Artsakh farmers²⁶

Nikol Pashinyan took to Twitter on Monday to denounce the latest shooting by Azerbaijani soldiers at farmers in Artsakh (Nagorno-Karabakh). He presented

²⁰ <https://jam-news.net/russian-mp-threatened-azerbaijan-with-a-nuclear-strike-the-kremlin-had-to-intervene>

²¹ <https://news.am/rus/news/729766.html>

²² P. Zalewski

https://twitter.com/p_zalewski/status/1326031395471437824?lang=gl

²³ <https://jam-news.net/georgia-azerbaijan-and-turkey-start-joint-military-exercises/>

²⁴ <https://www.panorama.am/en/news/2022/11/12/Armenia-challenges/2755234>

²⁵ <https://themuslimkashmir.com/2020/11/21/azerbaijans-troops-enter-first-district-handed-over-by-armenia/>

²⁶

<https://www.panorama.am/en/news/2022/11/14/Pashinyan-Azeri-shooting/2755620>

Azerbaijan's suggestions according to Artsakh (Nagorno-Karabakh) as a territory and its Armenian population as follows:

"Azerbaijan calls Armenians of Nagorno-Karabakh 'our citizens' and, at the same time, shoots at them while they're doing agricultural work," and as a counter suggestion Pashinyan noted "Is this the implementation of Azerbaijan's narrative saying 'the Nagorno-Karabakh issue is solved'?"

4.3. Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey start joint military exercises²⁷.

"Caucasian Eagle-2022" are joint military exercises being carried out by Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey. According to the information of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia, the opening ceremony of "Caucasian Eagle-2022" was held on October 11 in the village of Mukhrovani, at the military base of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia. The goal of the exercises is to achieve better synchronization in the actions of the special operations forces of the three countries, and to improve the effectiveness of command and control in a multinational environment. The units participating in the exercises will share their experience in conducting fire and medical training, combat operations in populated areas and special operations. As a result joint military exercises are threat against Russia, Iran and Armenia

4.4. . New agreement with Moscow: Threats against Azerbaijan from Russian information space to be blocked²⁸

The visit of Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov to Azerbaijan has been significant in many aspects. The most important one of them is, no doubt, signing an agreement on cooperation in the field of provision of international information security between two countries. Minister of Foreign Affairs Jeyhun Bayramov has signed an "Agreement on cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Government of the Russian Federation in the field of provision of international information security" with Sergey Lavrov on June 24.

4.5. Russia Supplies More Weapons to Azerbaijan²⁹

The Khrizantema-S anti-tank missile is a type of weapon Russia will be delivering to Azerbaijan

MOSCOW (RFE/RL)—Russia has delivered a new batch of anti-tank missile systems to Azerbaijan as part of lucrative arms deals with Baku that have been strongly criticized by Armenia over the past year.

The Azerbaijani Defense Ministry released over the weekend video of around a dozen self-propelled Khrizantema-S systems unloaded from a Russian cargo ship that docked at Baku's Caspian Sea port.

Khrizantema-S is designed to detect and destroy tanks, armored vehicles, field fortifications and even some low-flying aerial targets with guided missiles. It entered service with the Russian Armed Forces in 2005.

Russia has also sold around \$5 billion worth of tanks, artillery systems and other weapons to Azerbaijan in line with defense contracts signed in 2009-2011. According to the United Nations Register of Conventional Arms, it shipped six heavy artillery systems to the Azerbaijani military last year. Armenian leaders stepped up their criticism of those arms deals following Azerbaijan's April 2016 offensive in Nagorno-Karabakh. They said that the arms supplies run contrary to Russia's military alliance in Armenia and encourage Baku to attempt a military solution to the Karabakh conflict. Russian Prime Minister Dmitry Medvedev rejected the Armenian criticism after visiting Yerevan later in April 2016. He said that that Russia delivers weapons to both Armenia and Azerbaijan and thereby sustains the "military balance" in the conflict. In August, Russian President Vladimir Putin similarly denied that Moscow has increased the risk of another Karabakh war. Speaking after talks in the Kremlin with his Armenian counterpart Serzh Sarkisian, Putin implied that oil-rich Azerbaijan could have purchased offensive weapons from other nations. He also argued that Russia has long been providing substantial military aid to Armenia.

V. Azerbaijan's threats against Iran

5.1. Israel may be looking to strengthen ties to Azerbaijan as an Iran counter Azerbaijan threats Iran through the strengthening military ties with Israel. From 2016–2020, Israel accounted for 69 percent of Azerbaijan's major arms imports — a number that represents 17 percent of Israel's arms exports for that same period. TEL AVIV — With all signs indicating a new Iran nuclear deal is in the offing, Israel is looking for new ways to challenge Tehran — including tightening defense ties with Azerbaijan, Iran's northern neighbor. 5.2. Turkey, Azerbaijan are holding joint military exercises The Azerbaijani Defense Ministry said Friday that the air forces of Azerbaijan and Turkey will begin Monday to perform a joint military drill. The Turkish Air Force military personnel and aircraft that will participate in the TurAz Qartalı 2022 (TurAz Eagle 2022) Joint Flight-Tactical Exercises in Azerbaijan, it said. "Tasks on the planning of joint activities of the Air Forces of the two countries, the study of interaction and combat interoperability, as well as the carrying out search-and-rescue measures will be fulfilled during the exercises," it added.

5.3. . Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey start joint military exercises³⁰.

"Caucasian Eagle-2022" are joint military exercises being carried out by Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey. According to the information of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia, the opening ceremony of "Caucasian Eagle-2022" was held on October 11 in the village of Mukhrovani, at the military base of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia. The goal of the exercises is to achieve better synchronization in the actions of the spe-

²⁷ <https://jam-news.net/georgia-azerbaijan-and-turkey-start-joint-military-exercises>

²⁸ <https://apa.az/en/political/new-agreement-with-moscow-threats-against-azerbaijan-from-russian-information-space-to-be-blocked-analysis-379357>

²⁹ <https://anca.org/russia-supplies-more-weapons-to-azerbaijan/>

³⁰ <https://jam-news.net/georgia-azerbaijan-and-turkey-start-joint-military-exercises>

cial operations forces of the three countries, and to improve the effectiveness of command and control in a multinational environment. The units participating in the exercises will share their experience in conducting fire and medical training, combat operations in populated areas and special operations. As a result joint military exercises are threat against Russia, Iran and Armenia

VI Turkey’s threats against Iran

6.1. Turkiye, Azerbaijan are holding joint military exercises

The Azerbaijani Defense Ministry said Friday that the air forces of Azerbaijan and Turkiye will begin Monday to perform a joint military drill. The Turkish Air Force military personnel and aircraft that will participate in the TurAz Qartalı 2022 (TurAz Eagle 2022) Joint Flight-Tactical Exercises in Azerbaijan, it said. "Tasks on the planning of joint activities of the Air Forces of the two countries, the study of interaction and combat interoperability, as well as the carrying out

search-and-rescue measures will be fulfilled during the exercises," it added.

6.2. . Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey start joint military exercises³¹ .

“Caucasian Eagle-2022” are joint military exercises being carried out by Georgia, Azerbaijan and Turkey. According to the information of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia, the opening ceremony of “Caucasian Eagle-2022” was held on October 11 in the village of Mukhrovani, at the military base of the Ministry of Defense of Georgia. The goal of the exercises is to achieve better synchronization in the actions of the special operations forces of the three countries, and to improve the effectiveness of command and control in a multinational environment. The units participating in the exercises will share their experience in conducting fire and medical training, combat operations in populated areas and special operations. As a result joint military exercises are threats against Russia, Iran and Armenia.

Simulation models

Further we’ll consider as initial conditions for the model (2) military expenditures of countries given in the table as follows

Let us use notation of countries as follows

Notation	1	2	3	4	5
Country	Armenia	Azerbaijan	Russia	Iran	Turkey

Further we’ll consider as initial conditions for the model (2) military expenditures of countries given in the table as follows

Military expenditures of countries³²

Country	Armenia	Azerbaijan	Russia	Iran	Turkey
Military expenditures bln	1.39	2.81	65.9	24.5	15.5

Using the nature of threats given above we’ll consider matrixes presenting results of threats as follows.

Matrix 1. Threats between countries.

	AM	AZ	RU	R	TU
AM		1	1	1	1
AZ	30		30	30	
RU	1	7		1	1
IR		13	1		3
TU	20		13	15	

Current matrix as a simulation model gives number of imaginary threats between countries and allows to assess values of the coefficients d_{ij} , where $i \neq j, i, j = 1,2,3,4,5$.

Eigenvalues $\lambda_i, i = 1,2,3,4,5$ of the system (2) based on the matrix 2 is as follows:

26.94	-21.99	1.53	-2.61	-0.87
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And Eigenvectors $\alpha_{ij}, i, j = 1,2,3,4,5$ are as follows

AM	AZ	RU	IR	TU
-0.07	0.79	0.24	0.04	0.39
-0.02	0.79	-0.22	0.42	0.38
-0.3	0.11	0.35	0.35	-0.88
0.43	0.14	-0.35	-0.35	-0.82
0.22	0.01	-0.79	-0.79	0.02

Let us denote the general solution of the system (2) as

³¹ <https://jam-news.net/georgia-azerbaijan-and-turkey-start-joint-military-exercises>

³² <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/military-spending-by-country>

$$p_k(t) = \sum_{i=1}^5 C_i \exp(\lambda_i t) \alpha_{ki}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, 5. \quad (3)$$

Thus, based on the Matrix 1 we defined assessments for coefficients $C_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ as follows

8.779977	C1
-12.4622	C2
-65.7823	C3
11.54948	C4
11.19208	C5

As the assessments of military expenditures using (3) and values of eigenvalues and eigenvectors we have

t	AM	AZ	RU	IR	TU
1	1.713845	2.598305	66.24742	24.02705	15.57422
1.01	2.072485	3.065956	65.81962	25.008	15.75408

Assuming that the development of threats given above countries are able to change the policy of threats and make a decision concerning to the military expenditures. Through this assumption we could consider as simulation model based on the matrix presenting threats as follows

Matrix 2. Threats between countries

	AM	AZ	RU	R	TU
AM	0	10	1	1	5
AZ	12	0	2	3	2
RU	2	30	0	2	30
IR	1	20	2	0	10
TU	6	2	2	6	0

As eigenvalues and eigenvectors we have assessments as follows:

Eigenvalues $\lambda_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ of the system (2) based on the matrix 2 is as follows:

21.84	-14.96	2.38	-3.07	-6.18
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Eigenvectors $\alpha_{ij}, i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ are as follows

AM	AZ	RU	IR	TU
0.19	0.26	0.79	0.45	0.27
-0.08	0.21	-0.88	-0.33	0.25
-0.27	-0.19	0.89	0.15	0.27
-0.1	-0.04	0.97	-0.19	-0.04
0.13	0.004	-0.97	-0.01	0.2

Thus, based on the Matrix 1 we defined assessments for coefficients $C_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ as follows

C1	0.803956198
C2	0.285817634
C3	12.76883504
C4	4.468091662
C5	3.794506622

As the assessments of military expenditures using (3) and values of eigenvalues and eigenvectors we have

	t=1	t=1.01
AM	1.367097	2.233588
AZ	2.528327	3.381231
RU	65.84344	66.92612
Ir	25.21085	26.31822
TU	15.49906	16.32015

Conclusion.

We proposed an approach to study military expenditures of countries acting in conflicting region based on the Richardson model. Taking into consideration existence of five countries having interests in such

region as the region of South Caucasus we proposed a method for the modeling and solution of Richardson model as a case study. Among these countries we distinguished two countries Armenia and Azerbaijan

which have interests and conflicting caused by the disorder of territorial integrity and as a consequence interacting for the exhausting of economic and military resources of one another. The model considers also the group of countries interacting with these two distinguished countries as well having mutual interactions and interests in the region separately from distinguished two countries. The general model is proposed and the solution of this model is given. As the outcome of considered model the simulation model as the example of five countries having interests in the region is considered as simulation model. The simulation model allows to involve changes on the assessment of constants as the military expenditures outcome of interactions between countries. The numerical scheme is produced to provide the solution of general model as well of simulation model. Farther, the simulation model provides the schema for the enhancement of the number of entities of the model, define constants as outcomes of interactions between entities. (countries as considered in Richardson model). We argue that Richardson model allows the enhancements as means to adjust economic military expenditures policy in the region as the region of conflicting policies implementing by countries having opposite interests.

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